

TEYLOR VA MAKLOREN FORMULALARI VA UNGA DOIR MISOLLAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada funksiyalarni Teylor va Makloren formulalari yordamida ko'phadlar ko'rinishida ifodalash masalalari yoritilgan. Tadqiqot davomida qoldiq hading Koshi va Lagranj ko'rinishlari, shuningdek, elementar funksiyalarning Makloren qatoriga yoyilmalari tahlil qilingan. Maqolada keltirilgan amaliy misollar orqali limitlarni hisoblash va murakkab ifodalarni taqribiy qiymatlarini topishda ushbu formulalarning qulayligi va samaradorligi ko'rsatib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Teylor formulasi, Makloren formulasi, qoldiq had, hosila, taqribiy hisoblash, limit, yoyilma.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы представления функций в виде многочленов с помощью формул Тейлора и Маклорена. В ходе исследования проанализированы формы остаточного члена Коши и Лагранжа, а также разложения элементарных функций в ряд Маклорена. На практических примерах показана эффективность данных формул при вычислении пределов и нахождении приближенных значений сложных выражений.

Ключевые слова: формула Тейлора, формула Маклорена, остаточный член, производная, приближенное вычисление, предел, разложение

Abstract. This article examines the representation of functions as polynomials using Taylor and Maclaurin formulas. The research analyzes the Cauchy and Lagrange forms of the remainder term, as well as the Maclaurin series expansions of elementary functions. Practical examples demonstrate the effectiveness of these formulas in calculating limits and finding approximate values of complex expressions.

Keywords: Taylor formula, Maclaurin formula, remainder term, derivative, approximate calculation, limit expansion

KIRISH. Matematik analiz kursida funksiyalarning o'rganishning eng samarali usullaridan biri ularni soda ko'phadlar oraqali ifodalashdir. Teylor va Makloren Makloren formulalari murakkab funsiyalarni tahlil qilish, ularning nuqta atrofidagi xatti-harakatini aniqlash va hisoblash jarayonlarini soddalashtirish imkonini beradi. Ushbu ishning dolzarbligi matematik modellarni taqribiy hisoblashda xatoliklarni minimal darajaga tushurish usullarini o'rganish bilan belgilanadi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODLAR: Maqolani tayyorlashda Azlarov T. va Mansurov X. kabi olimlarning matematik analiz bo'yicha fundamental darsliklaridan hamda Demidovich B.P. ning masalalar to'plamidan foydalanildi.

Tadqiqotda matematik deduksiya, differensial hisob, funksiyalarni qatorga yoyish va matematik modellashtirish metodlaridan foydalanilgan. Xususan n-tartibli hosilaga ega funksiyalar uchun Teylor formulasi:

$$f(x) = f(x_0) + \frac{f'(x_0)}{1!}(x-x_0) + \frac{f''(x_0)}{2!}(x-x_0)^2 + \dots + \frac{f^{(n)}(x_0)}{n!}(x-x_0)^n + o((x-x_0)^n) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{f^{(k)}(x_0)}{k!}(x-x_0)^k + o((x-x_0)^n) \quad (f^{(0)}(x) = f(x))$$

ko'rinishida tahlil qilindi.

NATIJAR VA MUHOKAMA.

Tadqiqot natijasida quyidagi asosiy xulosalarga erishildi:

-Elementar funksiyalar $e^x, \sin x, \cos x, \ln(1+x)$ uchun Makloren formulalari tizimlashtirildi.

-Qoldiq hading Lagranj ko'rinishidan foydalanib $\alpha = \sin 36$ va $\beta = (1, 2)^{1,1}$ kabi miqdorlarni yuqori aniqlikda taqribiy hisoblash tartibi ko'rsatildi.

Limitlarni hisoblashda $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \frac{e^x \sin x - x(1+x)}{x^3}, \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left[x - x^2 \cdot \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{x} \right) \right]$ ko'rinishidagi

aniqmasliklarni ochishda Teylor yoyilmasining samaradorligi isbotlandi.

Funksiyaning Teylor va Makloren formulasi va unga doir misollar

$y = f(x)$ funksiya x_0 nuqtaning ($x_0 \in \square$) biror atrofida berilgan bo'lsin. Agar funksiya x_0 nuqtaning shu atrofida $y = f'(x), f''(x), \dots, f^{(n-1)}(x)$ hosilalarga ega bulib, x_0 nuqtada n-tartibli $f^{(n)}(x_0)$ hosilaga ega balsa, u holda

$$f(x) = f(x_0) + \frac{f'(x_0)}{1!}(x-x_0) + \frac{f''(x_0)}{2!}(x-x_0)^2 + \dots + \frac{f^{(n)}(x_0)}{n!}(x-x_0)^n + o((x-x_0)^n) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{f^{(k)}(x_0)}{k!}(x-x_0)^k + o((x-x_0)^n) \quad (f^{(0)}(x) = f(x))$$

(1) bo'ladi. Bu Teylor formulasidir.

2. Makloren formulasi. Agar (1) formulada $x_0 = 0$ deb olsak, unda ushbu

$$f(x) = f(0) + \frac{f'(0)}{1!}x + \frac{f''(0)}{2!}x^2 + \dots + \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!}x^n + o(x^n) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{f^{(k)}(0)}{k!}x^k + o(x^n) \quad (2)$$

formula hosil bo'ladi. Bu Makloren formulasidir.

Ushbu $f(x) = e^x, f(x) = \sin x, f(x) = \cos x, f(x) = (1+x)^m, f(x) = \ln(1+x)$ funksiyalar uchun (2) Makloren formulasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$1) e^x = 1 + x + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \dots + \frac{x^n}{n!} + o(x^n),$$

$$2) \sin x = x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^5}{5!} - \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \frac{x^{2n-1}}{(2n-1)!} + o(x^{2n}),$$

$$3) \cos x = 1 - \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^4}{4!} - \dots + (-1)^n \frac{x^{2n}}{(2n)!} + o(x^{2n+1}),$$

$$4) (1+x)^m = 1 + mx + \frac{m(m-1)}{2!}x^2 + \dots + \frac{m(m-1)\dots(m-n+1)}{n!}x^n + o(x^n)$$

$$5) \ln(1+x) = x - \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} - \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \frac{x^n}{n} + o(x^n)$$

Teylor formulasi (oraliq uchun).

$y = f(x)$ funksiya $[a, b]$ segmentda berilgan bo'lsin. Agar funksiya shu segmentda $f'(x), f''(x), \dots, f^{(n-1)}(x)$

hosilalarga ega bo'lib, x_0 nuqtada ($a < x_0 < b$) $f^{(n+1)}(x)$ hosilaga ega bo'lsa, u holda

$$f(x) = f(x_0) + \frac{f'(x_0)}{1!}(x-x_0) + \frac{f''(x_0)}{2!}(x-x_0)^2 + \dots + \frac{f^{(n)}(x_0)}{n!}(x-x_0)^n + R_n(x)$$

bo'ladi. Bu *Taylor formulasidir*. $R_n(x)$ ni Taylor formulasining qoldiq hadi deyiladi. U quyidagi ko'rinishlarga ega:

$$1) R_n(x) = \frac{f^{(n+1)}(c)}{n!}(x-x_0)^{n+1}(1-\theta)^n \text{ (Koshi ko'rinishi). } (c = x_0 + \theta(x-x_0), 0 < \theta < 1)$$

$$2) R_n(x) = \frac{f^{(n+1)}(c)}{(n+1)!}(x-x_0)^{n+1} \text{ Lagranj ko'rinishi, } (c = x_0 + \theta(x-x_0), 0 < \theta < 1)$$

1-misol. Ushbu $f(x) = \sqrt{x}$ funksiyani $x-1$ ning manfiy bo'lmagan darajalari bo'yicha yoyilmasining uchta xadini toping. Bu hol uchun (1) formula ushbu

$$f(x) = f(1) + \frac{f'(1)}{1!}(x-1) + \frac{f''(1)}{2!}(x-1)^2 + 0((x-1)^2)$$

ko'rinishda bo'ladi. Berilgan funksiyaning hosilalarini topamiz:

$$f'(x) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}}, f''(x) = -\frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{x^3}}$$

Ravshanki,

$$f(1) = 1, f'(1) = \frac{1}{2}, f''(1) = -\frac{1}{4}$$

$$\text{Demak, } \sqrt{x} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}(x-1) - \frac{1}{8}(x-1)^2 + 0((x-1)^2)$$

2-misol. Agar $x \rightarrow 0$ da

$$f(x) = 1 + \frac{1}{2}x + 0(x)$$

bo'lsa,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} [f(x)]^{\frac{1}{x}} = \sqrt{e}$$

bo'lishini isbotlang.

Ushbu

$$y = [f(x)]^{\frac{1}{x}}$$

funksiyani qaraylik. Uni quyidagicha

$$y = e^{\ln[f(x)]^{\frac{1}{x}}} = e^{\frac{1}{x} \ln[f(x)]}$$

ko'rinishda yozish mumkin. Agar

$$\ln f(x) = \ln \left[1 + \frac{1}{2}x + 0(x) \right]$$

Hamda

$$\ln \left[1 + \frac{1}{2}x + 0(x) \right] = \frac{1}{2}x + 0(x)$$

bo'lishini e'tiborga olsak, unda

$$y = e^{\frac{1}{x}\left(\frac{1}{2}x+0(x)\right)} = e^{\frac{1}{2}+\frac{0(x)}{x}}$$

bo'lishini topamiz. Keyingi tenglikdan

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} y = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} [f(x)]^{\frac{1}{x}} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \left(e^{\frac{1}{2}+\frac{0(x)}{x}} \right) = \sqrt{e}$$

ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

3-misol. Teylor formulasidan foydalanib ushbu

$$\alpha = \sin 36, \quad \beta = (1,2)^{1,1}$$

miqdorlarni taqribiy hisoblang.

(3) formulaga asoslanib

$$\sin x = x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^5}{5!} + 0(x^5)$$

munosabatga va undan ushbu

$$\sin x \approx x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^5}{5!}$$

taqribiy formulaga kelamiz. Bu taqribiy formuladan foydalanib, topamiz:

$$\alpha = \sin 36 = \sin \frac{\pi}{5} \approx \frac{\pi}{5} - \frac{1}{6} \cdot \frac{\pi^3}{125} + \frac{1}{5!} \cdot \frac{\pi^5}{5^5} \approx 0,588$$

Demak,

$$\alpha \approx 0,588$$

(3) formulaga asoslangan holda

$$(1+x)^m = 1 + mx + \frac{m(m-1)}{2!}x^2 + 0(x^2)$$

bo'lishiga ega bo'lamiz. Bundan esa

$$(1+x)^m \approx 1 + mx + \frac{m(m-1)}{2!}x^2 + 0(x^2)$$

taqribiy formulaga kelamiz.

Endi shu formuladan foydalanib β miqdorni taqribiy hisoblaymiz:

$$\beta = (1,2)^{1,1} = 1,2 \cdot (1,2)^{0,1} = 1,2 \cdot (1+0,2)^{0,1} \approx 1,2 \cdot \left(1 + 0,1 \cdot 0,2 + \frac{0,1 \cdot (-0,9)}{2} \cdot 0,2^2 \right) \approx 1,121$$

Demak,

$$\beta \approx 1,121.$$

4-misol. (3) formulalardan foydalanib ushbu

$$a) \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \frac{e^x \sin x - x(1+x)}{x^3}$$

$$b) \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left[x - x^2 \cdot \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{x} \right) \right]$$

limitlarni toping.

a) da ko'rsatilgan limitni topishda (3) formulaning quyida

$$e^x = 1 + x + \frac{x^2}{2!} + o(x^2),$$

$$\sin x = x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + o(x^3)$$

holidan foydalanamiz

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^x \sin x - x(1+x)}{x^3} &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\left[1 + \frac{x}{1!} + \frac{x^2}{2!} + o(x^2)\right] \left[x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + o(x^3)\right] - x(1+x)}{x^3} = \\ &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x + x^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{6}\right)x^3 + o(x^3) - x - x^2}{x^3} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{1}{3}x^3 + o(x^3)}{x^3} = \frac{1}{3} + \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{o(x^3)}{x^3} = \frac{1}{3} \end{aligned}$$

Demak,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \frac{e^x \sin x - x(1+x)}{x^3} = \frac{1}{3}$$

b) da ko'rsatilgan limitni topishda (3) formulaning

$$\ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right) = \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{2}{x}\right)^2 + o\left(\frac{1}{x^2}\right)$$

holidan foydalanamiz.

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left[x - x^2 \cdot \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right) \right] = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left[x - x^2 \left(\frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{2x^2} + o\left(\frac{1}{x^2}\right) \right) \right] = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left[x - x + \frac{1}{2} + o\left(\frac{1}{x^2}\right) \right] = \frac{1}{2}$$

Demak,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \frac{e^x \sin x - x(1+x)}{x^3} = \frac{1}{2}$$

5-misol. Quyidagi funksiyalarni Makloren formulasi bo'yicha $o(x^2)$ hadgacha yoying:

a) $f(x) = e^{\sqrt{1+2x}}$

b) $f(x) = \ln \cos x$

a) da ko'rsatilgan funksiyani Makloren qatoriga yoyish uchun Teylor qatoriga yoyish formulasida $x_0 = 0$ deb olib quyidagi formuladan foydalanamiz:

$$f(x) = f(0) + \frac{f'(0)}{1!}(x-0) + \frac{f''(0)}{2!}(x-0)^2 + o((x-0)^2) = f(0) + \frac{f'(0)}{1!}x + \frac{f''(0)}{2!}x^2 + o(x^2)$$

Berilgan funksiyani hosilalarini topamiz

$$f'(x) = \left(e^{\sqrt{1+2x}}\right)' = e^{\sqrt{1+2x}} \cdot (\sqrt{1+2x})' = e^{\sqrt{1+2x}} \cdot \frac{2}{2\sqrt{1+2x}} = \frac{e^{\sqrt{1+2x}}}{\sqrt{1+2x}}$$

$$f''(x) = \left(\frac{e^{\sqrt{1+2x}}}{\sqrt{1+2x}} \right)' = \frac{(e^{\sqrt{1+2x}})' \cdot \sqrt{1+2x} - (e^{\sqrt{1+2x}}) \cdot (\sqrt{1+2x})'}{(\sqrt{1+2x})^2} = \frac{\frac{e^{\sqrt{1+2x}}}{\sqrt{1+2x}} \cdot \sqrt{1+2x} - e^{\sqrt{1+2x}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+2x}}}{1+2x} = \frac{e^{\sqrt{1+2x}}(\sqrt{1+2x}-1)}{\sqrt{(1+2x)^3}}$$

ndi $x_0 = 0$ nuqtadagi qiymatlarni topamiz:

$$f(0) = e$$

$$f'(0) = e$$

$$f''(0) = 0$$

Hosil bo'lgan qiymatlarni formulaga qo'yamiz va quyidagini hosil qilamiz,

$$f(x) = e^{\sqrt{1+2x}} = e + e \cdot x + \frac{0 \cdot x^2}{2!} + 0(x^2)$$

b) da ko'rsatilgan funksiya uchun ham shunday ishlarni amalga oshiramiz.

$$f(0) = 0$$

$$f'(0) = 0$$

$$f''(0) = -1$$

$$f(x) = \ln \cos x = 0 + \frac{0 \cdot x}{1!} + \frac{(-1) \cdot x^2}{2!} + 0(x^2)$$

Demak,

$$\ln \cos x = -\frac{x^2}{2} + 0(x^2)$$

XULOSA

Taylor va Makloren formulalari nafaqat nazariy matematikada, balki amaliy muhandislik hisob-kitoblarida ham poydevor hisoblanadi. Maqolada keltirilgan misollar va tahlillar talabalarga murakkab funksiyalarni differentsiallashtirish orqali sodda ko'rinishga keltirish ko'nikmasini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi.

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